

Discover

Stage 1

Use the wheel to identify a wide range of information relevant to the problem statement.

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Define

Stage 2

Organise the information into themes, arriving at the real problem you want to solve. Spell out your aims.

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Design

Stage 3

Brainstorm a range of practical solutions to the problem you want to solve.

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Develop

Stage 4

Use the graph to help you review the impact and feasibility of the best solutions.

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Deliver

Stage 5

Use the set diagram to identify processes and methods to deliver the solution with the most potential.

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Distribute

Stage 6

Map out a framework to distribute and scale your solution.

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